

FOREST CARBON STOCKS ESTIMATION USING MULTIREOLUTION SATELLITE IMAGERY THROUGH SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE (SVM) APPROACH (A Literature Review)

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Abstract

Study to be conducted with the aimed to developing new methods for estimating tropical forest carbon stock using multi-resolution and multi-temporal satellite imagery with support vector machine (SVM) approach. To cover large area, a coarse resolution imagery of MODIS with seven band will be use as an input and high resolution imagery-QUICKBIRD for training data. The main approach in the study will comprises four steps deriving forest cover vegetation (forest type and forest density) from QUICKBIRD imagery using clustering algorithm, constructing predictor variables derived from MODIS satellite imagery such as surface reflectance, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), normalized difference soil index (NDSI) and one ground-measured variable - shortwave radiation, Train the SVM using predictor, apply extended domain of SVM for regression approximation and evaluate model performance and accuracy assessment based on coefficient of determination R² and a root mean square error (RMSE).

Kata kunci: forest carbon, stock estimation, satellitei imagery, Support vector machine

1. Introduction

Understanding the spatial patterns and processes of deforestation and degradation in developing countries to reduce carbon emissions are an important center in the fight against climate change. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions from fossil-fuel burning and industrial processes have been accelerating at a global scale, with their growth rate increasing from 1.1 percent per year for 1990–1999 to more than 3 percent per year for 2000–2004 [13]

Carbon is released into the atmosphere as carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions when forests are cleared or destroyed. Tropical deforestation is estimated to have been released from the order of 1-2 billion tons of carbon per year during the 1990s, approximately 15-25% of annual global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [5]. According with [6] deforestation and forest degradation in tropic area account for up to 30 percent of antropogenic carbon emission. High CO₂ in the atmosphere causes the GHG effect that contributes to increase global warming. During the 20th century, global surface temperature increased about 0.74 °C and using computer models of climate system based on six GHG emission scenario, projected that global

surface temperature will be increase from 1.1 °C to 6.4 °C until 2100 [8].

The one responsible to reduce carbon emissions is to protect and reduce the rate of deforestation. Deforestation, defined as conversion from forest land to non-forest land (UNFCCC definition). Vegetation has the ability to store carbon and can be identified and measured for the mitigation of climate change [4] because the exclusively a function of vegetation as a carbon reservoir [12]. Assumption that the differences in percentage of forest vegetation cover is able to store a different amount of carbon; the changes of vegetation cover in spatial and temporal term are used as model to calculate annual global changes of carbon emission.

Reduce carbon emissions from deforestation depends on accurate and precise estimates [16] and according to [4], several component must be estimated; loss of forest cover at the national level, initial carbon stocks for the base period and their change caused by deforestation and degradation and emissions averted from a defined “baseline” or base period.

Multi resolution and multi temporal remote sensing data combined with ground measurements plays a key role in determining loss of forest vegetation cover for stock carbon estimation and monitoring in large spatial scale in period of time.

Technical capabilities have advanced since the early 1990s and operational forest monitoring systems at the national level are now feasible goal for most developing countries [4]. The development of new technologies and approaches to remotely sense forest carbon stocks using satellite sensors have been conducting [17] [12] [6], although too costly for large areas, the methods could be used to extrapolate carbon stock estimates over larger regions [4] [12].

Following the development of remote sensing technology especially in sensor capability to produce high resolution images and computer algorithm processing, open the opportunity to develop method of estimating carbon stock more detailed using combining various resolution of satellite imagery, field measurement and computer modelling.

Study to be conducted with the aimed to developing new methods for estimating tropical forest carbon stock using multi-resolution and multi-temporal satellite imagery with support vector machine (SVM) approach

2. Literature Review

Estimating and monitoring carbon has been widely studied by researchers at the scale of space and different methodologies in the context of the obligations of each country for implementation of the Kyoto Protocol to reduce carbon emissions from deforestation. According with [5], estimation of carbon forest can be done in three ways including biome average method, forest inventory and satellite imagery data. Satellite data that can be used in mapping and monitoring carbon stock can be synthetic aperture radar (SAR), light detection and ranging-LIDAR [1] or optical satellite data [6]. The use of optical satellite imagery to date has been widely used in the study of carbon estimation because it has a high sensitivity optical reflectancy on a wide variety of structural canopy although the cloud-free imagery for sustainable use is still a problem [6].

Currently the use of different spatial resolution images or their combination commonly used in the estimation of carbon as it has been implemented by [10] [9] [21] in which their using combination low resolution image (MODIS) and medium resolution imagery (ASTER and LANDSAT). [12] conducted his research using combination low resolution imagery (MODIS) and high resolution Imagery (QUICKBIRD) and others researcher in the same domain only using single resolution such as using low resolution [15] or using medium resolution [17]. The use of large-resolution satellite imagery such as IKONOS and QUICKBIRD are yet not widely used mainly for estimation and monitoring in national and global scale, although the use of large-resolution imagery makes it possible to calculate the tree allometrik and

its relationship with the crown area to estimate the value of carbon is more detail [5].

According with [6], currently have been developed various approaches to estimate carbon stock using remote sensing data such as stratify & multiply (BC) approach, combine & assign (CA) approach and direct remote sensing (DR) approach or known as machine learning techniques like artificial neural network (ANN) and regression tree. Regression tree is the most frequently used methods, such as in research conducted by [10] [9] [12] and [8], because the ability to effectively use proportion or continuous predictor data sets with different measurement scale [3].

Another method of machine learning abilities in various applications is the state of art in the field of pattern recognition [11] but has not been widely used, is the support vector machine (SVM). SVM is the best machine learning algorithms in classifying high-dimensional datasets [7]. The inductive principle behind SVM is structural risk minimization (SRM) [20] and According to [19], the risk of a learning machine (R) is bounded by the sum of the empirical risk estimated from training samples (Remp) and a confidence interval (Y): $R < R_{emp} + Y$. The strategy of SRM is to keep the empirical risk (Remp). xed and to minimize the confidence interval (Y), or to maximize the margin between a separating hyperplane and closest data points. SVM approach to estimate carbon stock up to now has not been used even if theoretically and its application in other fields such bioinformatic have been put SVM as the best available approach till recent. [7], used SVM approach for land cover mapping and classification and in the other researcher [22] used SVM for gross primary production (GPP) estimation in continental scale with combination between low resolution satellite imagery (MODIS) and AmeriFlux data.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data and Software Processing

To cover large area, a coarse resolution imagery of MODIS (250 m resolution) with seven band (band 1 – band 7 will be use as an input. For training data, high resolution imagery (QUICKBIRD) will be use. QUICKBIRD imagery are contain 2.44 meters multispectral resolution and 0.60 meters panchromatic resolution. Ground truth for field carbon stock measurements in the various classes of forest density and type of vegetation will be conducted with the aim to increase the estimation accuracy.

Software processing including Matlab, geographical information system (GIS) and image processing software– IDRISI. Hardware including high performance computer hardware and data storage. Handheald global positioning system (GPS),

calculator, radio communication, field book and measuring tape will be use for fields measurement activity.

3.2. Methodology

The main approach in the study will comprises four steps:

- Deriving forest cover vegetation (forest type and forest density) from QUICKBIRD imagery using clustering algorithm.
- Constructing predictor variables derived from MODIS satellite imagery such as surface reflectance, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), normalized difference soil index (NDSI) [18], shadow index (SI) [14] and one ground-measured variable - shortwave radiation [22].

NDVI is expressed as:

$$NDVI = (NIR - red) / (NIR + red)$$

Where NIR is band 2 and red is band 1 in MODIS spektral

NDSI is expressed as:

$$NDSI = (SWIR - NIR) / (SWIR + NIR)$$

Where SWIR is band 6 and NIR is band 2 in MODIS spektral.

SI is expressed as:

$$SI = [(255 - B) * (255 - G) * (255 - R)]^{1/3}$$

In where B is blue band, G is green band and R is red band responses

- Train the SVM using predictor and apply extended domain of SVM for regression approximation (Zhan et al, 2003 and Yang et al, 2006)
- Evaluate model performance and accuracy assessment based on coefficient of determination R² and a root mean square error (RMSE). RMSE indicate a good fit between the predicted and the training data (Yang et al, 2007, Rokmatuloh, 2008, Baccini et al, 2008)

4. Hypothesis

The hypothesis that can be delivered in this paper are :

- a) The combined use of high resolution satellite images as training data and its implementation at a large resolution image can produce estimates of forest carbon stock with better on a wider coverage area.

- b) Support Vector Machine (SVM) is an approach that could estimates of forest carbon is better on the incorporation of multiresolution satellite image data.

5. References

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